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ID: 202434010

EXPERIMENT NO: 04

EXPERIMENT NAME: Determination of Drilling mud viscosity by using Marsh Funnel Viscometer.

OBJECTIVE:

To determine the viscosity of drilling mud by measuring the time it takes for a certain volume of mud to flow through a Marsh Funnel viscometer.

THEORY:

Drilling mud is a mixture of water and mud (Clay) addition to some other minerals and special chemical materials called "additives" that used with water and mixed to maintain well stability during the process of drilling. Sometimes mud can be non-aqueous regarding to well condition that can be Oil-Base Mud used . The composition that required for drilling mud is depend upon the formation stability which wells are drill through formations with a different type of compositions that require different types of mud composition . The liquid-based mud which usually composed of a based fluid such as (Oil or Water) with some weighting additives such as Bentonite and Barite.

Drilling fluid viscosity is the thickness or resistance of the mud to flow. It shows how easily the fluid can move through the well. When the viscosity is high the fluid is thick and flows slowly. When the viscosity is low the fluid is thin and flows quickly. Viscosity is important because it helps carry the drill cuttings to the surface and keeps them suspended when the flow stops. It also helps reduce friction inside the well.

FIGURE 1 : Viscosity(pa.s) vs shear rate(s⁻¹)

Drilling mud is a shear-thinning fluid which means its viscosity goes down when it is stirred or pumped faster. It also becomes thinner at higher temperatures. The mud is thickest at 27°C and

thinnest at 85°C because heat reduces its resistance to flow. In deep wells where the temperature is high engineers need to adjust the mud so it keeps working properly under pressure and heat.

pH is important because it helps control corrosion, bacterial growth, and clay stability in the mud. Viscosity is how thick or thin the mud is, or how easily it flows. A thicker mud (high viscosity) carries rock cuttings better, while a thinner mud (low viscosity) flows more easily.

FIGURE 2: Viscosity varies on pH

Viscosity is measured using a tool called a Marsh Funnel. This funnel is cone-shaped with a diameter of about 152 mm (6 inches) at the top and a length of about 305 mm (12 inches). It can hold around 1500 cc of fluid. A mesh screen covers the top half of the funnel. This screen stops large particles like drilling cuttings from blocking the small hole at the bottom. The time it takes for one quart (946 ml) of fluid to flow through the hole shows how thick or thin the fluid is. This time tells us the viscosity, or how easily the fluid flows.

FIGURE 3: Marsh funnel viscometer.

Effective viscosity is how thick or thin a fluid actually flows when it is moving. Some fluids change their thickness depending on how fast they are poured or stirred. So, effective viscosity shows the real flow behavior of the fluid during use, not just when it is still. It helps us understand how the fluid will act in real situations like different speeds or temperatures.

FIGURE 4: Effective viscosity & activation time relation

The effective viscosity is determined from following simple formula,

$$\mu = \rho_m(t_m - 25)$$

Where, μ = effective viscosity in centipoise (cp)

ρ_m = density in gm/ cm³

t_m = quart funnel time in seconds

APPARATUS:

- Marsh Funnel
- Graduated Beaker
- Drilling Mud Balance
- PPE's (Personal Protective Equipments)

- Components for drilling mud: water: 1500 mL, bentonite: 86 g, baking Soda: 2 g & sodium Chloride: 15 g

PROCEDURE:

CALIBRATION:

- The funnel and cup were cleaned, and 1500 ml of water was added while the hole was blocked.
- The timer was started when the finger was removed, and stopped after 946 ml was collected.
- If the time was 26 ± 0.5 seconds, the viscometer was considered accurate.

PROCESS:

1. The clean, dry funnel was held upright, and the outlet was covered with the index finger. A fresh sample of the fluid was then poured into the funnel until it reached the bottom edge of the screen.

Figure 5: Pouring mud fluid in marsh funnel fluid

Figure 6: Releasing the mud fluid

2. The finger was removed from the outlet, and the timer was started. The measuring cup was used to record the time it took for the fluid to reach the one-quart (1500 mL) line. Record the time to the nearest second(28sec) to assess the Marsh Funnel viscosity and document the fluid's temperature(24 degree Celsius)

Figure 7: Measuring Outflow of Drilling Mud

Figure 8: Recording the nearest time

Using Measuring Cup

DATA COLLECTION TABLE:

Table 1: Properties for preparing the drilling mud

Components	Amount
Water	1500 ml
Bentonite	86 g
Baking Soda (NaHCO ₃)	2 g
Sodium Chloride (NaCl)	15 g

CALCULATION:

Here,

Specific gravity = 1.03

Specific gravity = ρ of mud / ρ of water

; ρ of mud = S.G * ρ of water
 [for water, $\rho = 1 \text{ gm/cc}$]

$$\rho \text{ of mud} = (1.03 * 1) \text{ gm/cc}$$

$$\therefore \rho_{mud} = 1.03 \text{ g/cc}$$

$$t_m = 28 \text{ sec}$$

$$\therefore \text{Mud viscosity, } \mu_c = \rho_m (t_m - 25)$$

$$= 1.03 (28 - 25)$$

$$= 3.09 \text{ cp}$$

RESULT:

The specific gravity of the mud was: 1.03 & Marsh Funnel viscosity of the prepared drilling mud was: 3.09 cp at 24 degree Celsius temperature.

DISCUSSION:

The prepared drilling mud had a specific gravity of 1.03, which means it was slightly heavier than water. This indicates that the mud had a low density, making it suitable for shallow wells or formations with low pressure. Using a lighter mud helps reduce the risk of damaging the formation or causing a blowout.

The Marsh Funnel viscosity was measured at 3.09 centipoise at a temperature of 24°C. This low viscosity shows that the fluid flows easily and can circulate well through the wellbore. However, fluids with low viscosity may not carry cuttings effectively, especially in deep wells or where the angle of drilling is high. This means the mud might need to be adjusted or thickened for more complex drilling operations.

Since the test was done at room temperature the values are reliable for understanding the mud's behavior under normal working conditions.

Overall, the mud is lightweight and has good flow properties, making it a good starting point for simple drilling jobs. But for harder drilling conditions additives may be needed to increase its density or viscosity.